

INNOVATIVE WAYS TO USE INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAMS IN THE TEACHING PROCESS

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Abstract: *This article provides analytical information on the theoretical basis, content, analysis of the methodology of assessment systems, the specifics of the use of international assessment systems in monitoring the knowledge of students in computer science. The emergence of a general educational standard in computer science, the need to get rid of admissibility and chaos in the study of this subject, the establishment of uniform requirements for mandatory, minimum required results for students, the methodology of testing and o Assessment of students' knowledge and skills plays an important role in improving the quality of education.*

Keywords— international assessment programs, assessment system, information technology in education, ICT.

1. INTRODUCTION

At a time when our country is developing rapidly on the path of innovative development, comprehensive support for the creative ideas and creativity of young people who are the successors of our future, the formation of their knowledge, skills and advanced foreign experience, international standards and to improve the system of assessment on the basis of requirements, to study international experience in this direction, a comprehensive comparative analysis of the existing system, close cooperation with relevant international and foreign organizations, research institutions.

The main purpose of the introduction of continuing education in the country is to form in the younger generation such skills as high professional culture, creative and socio-political activity, free thinking. First of all, it is necessary to increase the activity of students. Therefore, it is important to use a wide range of interactive teaching methods to develop students' independent, creative and critical thinking. At the same time, in the formation of knowledge and skills of students in the field of labor education, the organization of lessons and extracurricular activities is systematic, goal-oriented, the introduction of new methods of monitoring and evaluation of learning outcomes. 'z is not reflected. Therefore, the use of active methods of education and upbringing in the improvement of teaching methods in secondary schools, the search for ways to rationally use the optimal forms of teaching and testing is becoming a topical issue.

It is well known that teaching methods consist of the teacher's activities with students to achieve specific

goals, which serve to reveal the issues of who should be taught what and how. Therefore, the activation of students' cognitive activities and the selection of appropriate forms and methods for their independent, creative thinking will be effective in future training.

2. MAIN PART

Knowledge is subdivided into systematic and non-systemic, theoretical and practical, broad and narrow, deep and superficial, flexible, standardized, robust and unstable. These include increasing the theoretical and practical knowledge gained through vocational training. Because theoretical knowledge refers to the sufficient properties of things (objects), the phenomenon of techniques and technologies and their objective relationship. Practical knowledge, on the other hand, refers to the connection of processes in the field of engineering and technology, events, and so on, to the direct practical application of them.

In the process of testing and evaluating students' knowledge, skills, and competencies, the teacher has consistently influenced individual students and the whole class community, combining individual work with classroom work. Experienced teachers o' rely on the opinion of the class team in the process of assessing student knowledge and have an educational impact on students. In doing so, the teacher activates the attention of the class and teaches them to take responsibility for their peers' responses. It also helps them to consolidate their knowledge and take a critical look at their own knowledge. This teaches the student to be honest and truthful at the right time.

When assessing knowledge, the teacher takes into account the characteristics of the student, such as the level of mastery of the material, the level of growth of

the child's thinking, the development of the brain: the speed of work, ability, desire to read, speech swelling rate is studied. It also eliminates the characteristics of dryness, shyness, shyness, overestimation of self-esteem, distrust, haste, short-sightedness that occur in some students. As a result, the harmony of teacher and student activities in the educational process mined.

The educational value of testing and evaluating knowledge, skills, and competencies is that they develop students' attitudes toward learning, their own successes and failures, and their desire to overcome difficulties. Assessment always creates a certain attitude towards oneself as a student, as a person. The teacher skillfully uses this attitude towards the student, these feelings in the formation of such qualities in his actions as willpower, community, mutual assistance.

The use of interactive multimedia technology in the classroom is not a respect for fashion, it is not a way to transfer a teacher's multifaceted creative work to a computer, but it is one of the tools that allows:

- activation of the educational process;
- increase cognitive activity;
- reduce fatigue and improve performance;
- Improving training efficiency.

Our pedagogical experience shows that interactive multimedia-rich classes are very popular among cadets, which contributes to the positive motivation of teaching physics.

As a result of the development of informatization, the demand for highly qualified teachers in the education system is growing. through creative educators with the skills and qualifications to apply information technology in practice, the problem of training young people who meet today's educational standards and are expected to become the country's leading cadres in the future arises. In view of the above, it can be acknowledged that this research work is one of the most relevant studies.

The fact that in recent years the country has achieved great economic growth as a result of reforms has further increased the demand for qualified personnel and qualified specialists in all areas.

This in itself requires increasing the interest of our students in the lessons and increasing the attention of teachers to comprehensive education.

The fact that the above requirements are very important for the education system means that, as in most foreign countries, it is necessary to attract best

practices to improve the quality of education by assessing and monitoring the development of education and science.

First of all, it is necessary to mention the results that Uzbekistan can achieve by participating in international surveys on the quality of education:

- It will be used to reform the national education system, improve the content of education, training and professional development programs for teachers, and create a new generation of textbooks by professionals.
- The results of the research allow us to draw conclusions about the quality of education in the country and its role, taking into account international standards.
- International research has a positive impact on the quality of national research in education.
- Allows the creation of a national evaluation system based on high economic efficiency at the level of international standards.
- Participation in international research with the involvement of leading experts from various organizations in Uzbekistan will develop a culture of monitoring research among our local experts, bringing the quality of education assessment in line with international standards.
- Allows the development of control materials in the assessment of the quality of national education at the level of quality of control materials used in international research.

3. CONCLUSION

The main purpose of the introduction of continuing education in the country is to form in the younger generation such skills as high professional culture, creative and socio-political activity, free thinking. First of all, it is necessary to increase the activity of students. Therefore, it is important to use a wide range of interactive teaching methods to develop students' independent, creative and critical thinking. At the same time, in the formation of knowledge and skills of students in the field of labor education, the organization of lessons and extracurricular activities is systematic, goal-oriented, the introduction of new methods of monitoring and evaluation of learning outcomes. 'z is not reflected. Therefore, the use of active methods of education and upbringing in the improvement of teaching methods in secondary schools, the search for ways to rationally use the optimal forms of teaching and testing is becoming a topical issue.

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